

A STUDY ON RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STRESS MANAGEMENT AND WORKABILITY

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ABSTRACT

There were many aspects that lead to the success of a business in an industry. HRM is one such significant area that makes a business grow. Stress management helps to increase the productivity in every business concern. Nowadays stress management is a valuable complement to traditional management concept. According to the potentiality of employees, companies were adopting the strategy, how to measure and manage the stress at individual level and organizational level. In our country organizational role stress and occupational stress were playing a vital role. A good stress management strategy is the most important aspect for the success of any kind of business. Strategy consists of the steps taken and procedures followed for managing or cope with stress. The function of stress management helps to develop and satisfy the emotional needs of each and every employee within the industry. Simultaneously it increases the performance of the organization as well as employee. This paper will concentrate on the obstacles to develop the strategy (managing stress) and provide guidance on how to implement that plan and monitor its effectiveness. The impact of stress with related to the productivity and performance of the employees and its reflection helps to develop consequences of stress model and overcoming the effectiveness

INTRODUCTION

Stress has nowadays become a prevalent state in everyday human life especially among different employees at various levels of job. On the one hand stress is the motivational force and on the other side it is the cause of depression. In fact the lack of stress is the end of life, as there is no enthusiasm towards the accomplishment of goals. When an employee is at the work place there are different stressors that are having a direct impact upon the performance of employees.

Stress can have serious implications for both the individual's health and performance. In terms of health, the relationship between stress and different serious illnesses has been scientifically established (e.g. Schleifer et al., 1983; Kiecolt-Glaser et al., 1985; Camara and Donao, 1989). Heart disease, depression, anxiety, low self-esteem, reduced job performance and burn-out are cases in point from a long list of negative outcomes of stress. Brummet et al. (cited in Cooper and Makin, 1984) asserted that managers suffer extreme physiological symptoms from stress at work, which compel them to premature retirement from work before they have had the opportunity to complete their potential organizational life. This is a serious loss to the organization in terms of valuable human resources and, consequently, financial ones. In terms of performance, decision making under stress becomes faulty. Instead of undertaking careful analysis or effective use of heuristics, the stressees (individual under stress) becomes trapped in a vicious circle of non-productive intuitive personal emotional needs.

WHAT IS STRESS?

People get sick from stress at work and the cost associated with stress is hence significant to the employer. Han Salye, probably the leading authority on the concept of stress, described stress as, 'the role of all wear and tear caused by life'. Stress is associated with constraints and demands. Constraints prevent the person from doing things what he or she desires. Demand refers to the loss of something desired. Stress is highest for the individuals who perceive they are uncertain as to whether they will win

or lose and lowest for those who think that winning or losing is a certainty. If winning or losing is an unimportant outcome, there is no stress. For example, if retaining the job or earning a promotion does not hold any importance for the person, the person has no reason to feel stress over having to Undergo a performance review. In short, we can define stress as a dynamic condition in which a person deals with a situation or constraint or demand related to his/her desire for which the outcome perceives to be both important and uncertain.

Organizations use several kinds of inputs, such as manpower, materials and capital. Peter F. Drucker, called the Management Guru quotes that 'The greatest opportunity for increasing productivity is surely to be found in knowledge work itself and especially in management'. In general, productivity improvement programs are mostly aimed at the worker level. Motivation and stress management play a **VITAL ROLE IN PRODUCTIVITY**.

Consequences of stress

Stress can have various effects on the individual as well as on the organization. Clearly not only the individual suffers but the organization may also be affected by absenteeism, work related accidents, turnover and impaired decision making. While stress is typically discussed in a negative context, it also has positive value. It offers potential gain, for example, the superior performance that an ophthalmologist gives during a complicated surgery. Such individuals often use stress positively to rise to the occasion and perform to their maximum. And hence the productivity rises.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STRESS AND PRODUCTIVITY (PERFORMANCE)

The inverted U relationship between stress and productivity is illustrated by Figure.1. From the organization's stand point, management may not be concerned when employee experience low to moderate level of stress. Such levels may lead to higher employee performance. But high levels of stress or even low levels sustained over a long period of time, can lead to reduced employee performance and thus require action by management. From the individuals standpoint even low levels of stress are likely to be perceived as undesirable. What management may consider as 'a positive stimulus that keeps the adrenaline running' is a very likely to be seen as 'excessive pressure' by the employee. Stress have an emotional impact on all type of organizations, regardless of whether it is a manufacturing industry or a service organization. Figure shows the effects of stress on a manufacturing industry and on a service organization. The end result of stress is more significantly noted in a service organization than in a manufacturing industry.

MANAGING STRESS

Individuals and organizations have attempted to deal With stress in various ways. Individuals, for example, May try to reduce stress through better management of their time, nutritious food, exercises, career Planning, change in jobs, promotion of psychological Health, relaxation, meditation and prayer. Time can be managed effectively by,

- Making daily list of activities to be accomplished
- Prioritizing activities by importance and urgency
- Scheduling activities according to the priority set
- Knowing the daily cycle and handling the most

Demanding parts of job during the high part Organization may provide counselling or recreation facilities or may improve the job design by matching the person with the job. A proper fit between Individual needs and the demands of the task will benefit both the individual and the organization.

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH STUDY:

To elaborate the stress and job performance
 To show relationship between these variables

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

Although the results reveal a positive relationship between job stress and performance but the current study cannot be generalized due to a limited sample size. Furthermore, in order to comprehend the factors that may put an effect upon job performance further studies should be initiated with larger sample size.

Methodology**Hypothesis**

H0: Stress does not affect the job performance

H1: Stress affects the job performance

RESEARCH DESIGN

A structured questionnaire was administered to receive the responses of the employees of different manager level bankers on the variables of research study.

Sampling Procedure: Random sampling was used to gather the responses of employees from various public sector organizations.

Instrument: Work-Stress Questionnaire by Gerard Hargreaves was adapted to collect data. It included 19 questions. Section A included questions pertaining to the demographic features whilst section B contained the stress related questions and section C comprised of the questions that measure the performance level relative to its three dimensions i.e. skills, efforts and working conditions

DATA ANALYSIS**Source: primary sources**

The figure 1 shows that 36(76.6%) of them were males while 11(23.4%) were females.

Demographic Features of Respondents

Figure 1: Gender Of Employees

Figure 2: Salary of the Employees

Source: primary sources

Figure 2 reflects the salary ranges of the employees, which shows 21 employees are between the range of Rs.10000-20000, while only 1 employee is between Rs.61000-70000.

Figure 3: Age of the Employees

Table 1: Independent Sample t-test

Variables	Significant	T
STRESS	.296	.272
SKILLS	.879	-.954
EFFORTS	.033*	-.158
WORKING CONDITIONS	.011*	-2.474

*SIGNIFICANT AT .05 LEVEL

Table 2: Correlation between Stress and workability (N=47) *SIGNIFICANT AT .05 LEVEL (Pearson Correlation (r))

VARIABLES	workability
STRESS	r=.315
	Sig=0.031

FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

Research finding of this research outcome states that there is highly significant positive relationship among the stress and the employee workability. As the performance include three dimensions i.e. skills, efforts and working conditions.

All of these dimensions are also having a positive direct relationship with the stress independent variable. Whereas on the other hand the demographics including the age, salary and gender. These factors are not showing any significant relationship between the employee's performance and the stress.

CONCLUSION

Undoubtedly in every organization, a small group of the working population suffers from stress. If the management consider stress as an individual problem and not as a management problem, then they have to meet out with the loss due to absenteeism, turn over, total cost of work-related accidents and work that is not up to the standards. The organization should handle stress positively to increase the productivity.

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